

The benefits of training for the development of employees' communication in the commercial sector of organizations

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Abstract

Enhancing knowledge is one of the driving forces behind human beings' pursuit of their best version. In a broad sense, effective communication is a desired skill sought by many, as it opens up significant opportunities in personal and professional life. Investing in individual and organizational growth involves acquiring capabilities that make a difference and facilitate interpersonal interactions. Within this context, the present article addresses communication as a competitive advantage and analyzes issues related to business oratory as a strategy for individual and organizational development, aiming to improve company outcomes. It employs a descriptive design and qualitative methodology, utilizing both primary and secondary sources. The overarching objective is to analyze the main benefits of training in developing employees' communication skills within the commercial sector of organizations. The research concludes that communication is the primary tool in the commercial sector, as knowledge of sales techniques, determination, and drive would be of little use without the ability to communicate effectively. Therefore, training in business oratory is fundamental. It is worth noting that emotional communication is the most challenging yet crucial aspect for establishing a connection between salesperson and customer. Unfortunately, many sales professionals leave substantial potential revenue untapped by disregarding the significance of providing personalized, empathetic, and relatable communication.

Keywords: Organizational Training; Emotional Communication; Business Oratory; Persuasion and Convincing; Organizational Results.

1 Introduction

Modern companies, faced with a highly competitive market scenario and increasingly demanding customers who receive a flood of information through the Internet every day, are realizing the need to modify their strategies within their own organizational environment. These strategies should not only impact customers and potential clients but also resonate with their hearts, understanding and respecting their profiles. As Dias (2010, p. 275) states, "the marketing professional needs to know in advance how the consumer will encode their message, which communication channels will reach them, and what their response will be to the communication stimulus [1]."

Action plans need to be well-crafted, with a focus on personalized service and, above all, clear, objective, assertive, persuasive, and emotionally engaging communication. The fundamental principle is that the customer is a human being, made of pure emotion, not a machine. Without a human connection, there will be no engagement or interest in the product or service offered.

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The methodology used in this article employs a descriptive and qualitative design, based on primary and secondary sources. The overall objective of this research is to demonstrate the main benefits of training for the development of communication skills among employees in the commercial sector of organizations. The specific objectives are as follows: to explain the nature of organizational training and its practice in companies; to discuss the contribution of communication to personal development; to link the practice of organizational training to the development of employee communication.

This article is structured into four sections. The first section is the introduction, where the research objectives are explained. The second section is reserved for the methodology. The third section is the theoretical framework, which promotes discussions related to the researched theme, and the fourth and final section presents the concluding remarks.

2 Material and methods

The methodology used in this article adopts a qualitative and descriptive approach, based on primary and secondary sources. According to Lakatos and Marconi (1999, p. 19), "descriptive research delineates what is, addressing four aspects: description, recording, analysis, and interpretation of current phenomena, aiming to understand their functioning in the present [2]."

Given the in-depth dedication to research other articles, books, theses, and journals, which involved analysis of other duly cited authors that served as the foundation for this work, a qualitative approach was employed to make the research more rigorous and reliable, aiming for it to become a significant source of research in the future.

In the academic field, the qualitative study of a social phenomenon has accompanied research in various areas, sparking debates about the path to follow, the steps to take, and which techniques and instruments to use in knowledge production [3].

During the research process in the elaboration of this article, there were often significant accumulations of information, but over time, they were organized and transformed into knowledge, always through the process of subtraction and addition, turning complexity into simplicity - "a tangle of actions, interactions, and feedbacks" [4].

Indeed, it is a great challenge, as the fear of facing the complexity of qualitative research can lead to self-sabotage - "we believe we see reality; in reality, we see what the paradigm asks us to see and conceal what the paradigm compels us not to see" [4].

Among the contributions that were researched, the works of authors such as Chiavenato (2006), Kotler et al. (2017), Hirschle et al. (2018), Ferreira et al. (2020), Luccas and Damian (2022) stand out. Thus, the knowledge gained from the researched authors aided in our creativity, as they provided essential insights into what has been produced about our object of study and the advances made in this area.

3 Literature Review

This foundation has been organized into 3 subsections. The first one discussed organizational training and its practice in companies. The second one focused on emotional communication and its development in salespeople as a highlight in the job market. The third one addressed the association of organizational training practice with the development of the communication skills of the sales team - explaining the concepts and the difference between persuasion and conviction.

3.1 How Organizational Training Works and Its Practice in Companies

Organizational training in companies is a structured and planned process aimed at developing and enhancing employees' skills, knowledge, and competencies to improve individual and collective performance, as well as organizational effectiveness and efficiency. It is a common practice in organizations of all sizes and sectors, playing a crucial role in the success and adaptation of companies to changes in the business environment.

It is essential to highlight that organizational training can cover a wide variety of areas, such as specific technical skills, leadership development, teamwork, communication, ethics, diversity, and inclusion, among other topics relevant to the business organization. Therefore, organizational training is a valuable tool to boost the growth and development of

companies, promote a healthy and motivating work atmosphere, and contribute to talent retention and attraction. In Table 1 below, you can observe the main stages that should be addressed in Organizational Training.

Table 1 Stages of Organizational Training

Diagnosis	Taking this first step is important to assess the needs and issues of the company and its employees. In this stage, all the aspects to be addressed in the training are pre-identified. One simple way to conduct this research is through questionnaires and data collection.
Planning	This post-diagnosis stage aims to plan the training, considering how, where, date, methodology, and deadlines. Adequate planning is fundamental to the success of a project. The most relevant points of this phase concern the strategies to be developed and their application, describing the overall structure of the training.
Implementation	Implementation or execution means actually carrying out an action or training step. You need to create an environment and work with your employees. It is essential that all equipment is functioning correctly to access all resources.
Evaluation	The last step after the training is to evaluate the performance of the professional, verify if all the steps were accomplished, and if it is accepted by the employees. This step is important to maintain your strategy and ensure that your actions have the expected results.

Source: [5]

As pointed out by Langhi (2019), organizational viability and competitive advantage go hand in hand with investments in employee training and development. In this sense, the continuous development of employees' skills and knowledge becomes a crucial factor for business success [6].

According to Chiavenato (2006, p. 288), training is defined as "the educational process, applied systematically, through which people learn knowledge, attitudes, and skills in relation to defined objectives [7]."

Undoubtedly, a well-trained employee makes all the difference in the company. Their enthusiasm and motivation in performing their routine activities are noticeable, as training impacts the improvement of their quality of life. Consequently, their work will be done with more dedication and commitment as a form of reciprocation, meaning that organizational processes will flow with more clarity and quality.

3.2 Emotional Communication and its Development among Sellers as a Highlight in the Job Market

Communication is one of the most important skills for any profession. According to Strunck (2011), a store must stimulate the consumer's five senses, providing them with a pleasant and unique experience, arousing emotions, and creating a relationship with the company [8].

In the organizational context, one of the topics that deserves to be reconsidered and applied with internal customers, i.e., employees, is humanized, inclusive, and non-violent communication, which should be used through all company channels. Psychologist Munnari (2022, p. 04) on the HR Portal website states, "humanized, inclusive, and non-violent communication should be used in all company communication channels, from informal dialogue to email, meetings, and more [9]."

Munnari (2022) further emphasizes the need for communication to be part of the company's culture and convey a sense of belonging. Hence, it is essential for managers to focus on the sales department, as it is the frontline sector that receives the most customer rejections. Therefore, these professionals require more specific attention through constant feedback to align communication. At the same time, leadership should foster a sense of team belonging so that they do not feel isolated and regain the motivation to move forward in search of more customers, ultimately achieving the organization's goals [9].

Unfortunately, companies leave a lot of money on the table by not knowing how to handle customers and not investing in communication training for their sales team. Indeed, there is still a significant gap between marketing and sales departments, and effective communication is a decisive factor in the success of any company. However, integration between departments is necessary for sales processes to flow naturally and successfully.

According to Lupetti (2007, p. 15), "Integrated communication establishes a global policy, based on the coherence between the programs established in institutional, administrative, internal, and marketing communications, in addition to avoiding task overlaps [10]".

Thus, integrated communication cannot be the result of individual efforts, as the company's image must be unified. "Communicative actions need to be guided by a philosophy and a policy of integration among its administrative, internal, institutional, and marketing modalities [11]."

Therefore, the decision-making process must be shared by all sectors of the organization. In short, organizational communication should not be fragmented or linear but rather holistic, integrated, and systemic. Communication plays a fundamental role in personal, professional, and social development, enabling the exchange of information, ideas, and experiences among individuals.

Marketing 4.0 is marketing of human emotions, social transformations, and a revolution in network interaction. In this sense, it is a period where brands need to humanize themselves to influence human relationships and reach their consumers [12].

The concept of Marketing 4.0 refers to a strategic approach to marketing that acknowledges the importance of digital and social transformations in the interaction between brands and consumers. It was popularized by renowned marketing authors Philip Kotler, Hermawan Kartajaya, and Iwan Setiawan (2017) in their book *Marketing 4.0: Moving from Traditional to Digital* [13].

Marketing 4.0 recognizes the importance of social transformations and seeks to leverage the opportunities provided by technology to engage consumers in a deeper and more meaningful way. This includes the use of social media platforms, personalized content, influencer marketing, and immersive brand experiences. The revolution in network interaction is a fundamental aspect of Marketing 4.0. The internet and social media play a central role in how brands communicate and interact with consumers.

"Marketing 4.0 leverages machine-to-machine (M2M) connectivity and artificial intelligence to increase marketing productivity while utilizing human-to-human connectivity to reinforce consumer engagement [13]". Marketing 4.0 emphasizes the need for brands to adapt to changes in consumer behavior driven by technology and digital era connectivity. It recognizes that consumers are increasingly empowered, informed, and connected, and their purchasing decisions are influenced by a variety of factors, including emotions and personal values.

With the transition to Marketing 4.0, it is necessary to place increasing importance on the centrality of humans to attract consumers in the digital era. Brands must reveal their human side to create human-to-human connections with consumers. It is essential to understand that there is no longer control over information, and consumers feel more comfortable and open to expressing their thoughts, with digital platforms driving this freedom of expression [14].

Communication plays a vital role in people's development, contributing to learning, professional growth, development of interpersonal skills, self-expression, self-awareness, and promotion of diversity. Another aspect worth highlighting is intrapreneurship in companies, considering that this practice leads to greater personal and professional results for each collaborator.

Intrapreneurship emerged to define the ideal type of collaborator that 21st-century organizations would need: someone who acts in their role or area of expertise with the mindset of an entrepreneur, as if they were the owner of the company for which they work [15].

Therefore, this change of paradigms is crucial, both on the part of management and employees, as internal and external processes need to communicate with greater autonomy and innovation, always seeking new improvements to expand the company's systemic vision. Organizational communication must be understood broadly and holistically, based on the principle that an employee who communicates with the owner's perspective will have greater productivity and will stand out as a differentiated professional in the job market.

3.3 Associating Organizational Training Practice with the Development of the Commercial Team's Communication

One way for employees to gain self-confidence and self-assertion in their competencies and abilities is through training. This practice helps them make more assertive decisions, reduce internal conflicts, as well as increase motivation and well-being in the organizational climate, consequently achieving the expected results.

It is of utmost importance that commercial managers advocate constant investment in training for the sales team and its leadership to put commercial development into practice, considering stimulating employee development, reducing work routine stress, and providing a sense of well-being by feeling valued and recognized.

There are several studies on well-being carried out in Brazil. Among them, the work of Hirschle, Gondim, Alberton, and Ferreira (2019, p. 532) stands out, where they state the following: "controlling the stress level in the work environment can help the worker preserve well-being at work by making better use of their regulatory processes [16]."

It is a fact that employee satisfaction in the work environment increases their state of happiness, thus guaranteeing organizational results. However, this practice must be associated with the theory learned in the classroom, requiring good management oversight to provide necessary feedback. "Organizations are made up of people and depend on them to achieve their objectives and fulfill their missions [7]."

Luccas and Damian (2022, p. 107) highlight that:

Communication, essential for human relations, is also relevant in the organizational environment since it contributes to companies becoming more successful in their businesses. In order to stand out in competitive environments, organizations need to rethink how they communicate internally, what their purposes are, and how the communication process interacts with people who act in the organizational context [17].

As a learning process in the commercial field, business oratory training, due to its exclusively commercial approach and being extremely necessary for sales professionals, undoubtedly presents a great opportunity to optimize communication by learning oratory techniques and public presentations, while becoming a more persuasive and convincing professional.

According to Gramigna et al. (2007), competency models are classified as the ability to work under pressure, entrepreneurship, negotiation, communication and interaction, creativity and innovation, initiative and dynamism, leadership, organization, planning, results-oriented, interpersonal relationship, decision-making, teamwork, and business vision [18].

Every employee within the organization, from the director to the intern, must communicate effectively, as the good or bad communication of each one can negatively or positively impact other processes. For example, in a company's sales department, achieving sales depends primarily on good communication between the salesperson, the client, and partners, making communication their main work input.

Good oratory is an essential skill for anyone. We live in constant communication and in many different ways, but some of them necessarily require eye contact. Knowing how to speak and write well is not enough for those who work in sales, as knowledge of persuasion and convincing techniques is extremely important.

For rhetorical discourse, it is not enough for the speaker to prepare. The audience is the central focus, which leads us to pathos, as there is no communication without communion, and no communion without the evocation of the passions and feelings of the public. Thus, it is common for the speaker, in the exordium, to already establish contact through exhortation, recognition, fear, pity, frustration, open confrontation against a declared adversary, social condition, morality, shared difficulties, pride, positive or negative achievements, social vices, justice and injustice, beauty and ugliness, in short, a series of initial discursive devices that lead to joy, sadness, longing, love, hatred, anger, rage, friendship, jealousy [...]. In short, to the passions of the audience [19].

It is essential for the speaker to be able to establish an emotional connection with the audience, arousing their passions and feelings. Effective communication requires communion between the speaker and the audience, where the speaker must identify and understand the needs and emotions of the audience to influence them significantly.

3.3.1 *Persuasion and Convincement.*

The Platonic dualism, based on the human soul, becomes quite clear: persuasion is directed towards emotion, and conviction towards reason. "What then is persuasion? It is leading someone to believe in something. Some strictly distinguish 'persuasion' from 'conviction,' the latter consisting not in making someone believe, but in making them understand. In our view, this distinction rests on an excessively dualistic philosophy - even an ideology - since it opposes, in man, the being of belief and feeling to the being of intelligence and reason [20]."

In Aristotle's Rhetoric (384-322 B.C.), the first definition of fable as a genre emerges. Conceiving rhetoric as a rigorous technique (*techné*) of argumentation and logical reasoning designed to convince, the Stagirite defines it as 'the ability to discover what is appropriate to each case in order to persuade,' that is, the 'faculty of discovering the means of persuasion on any given issue [21].'

With the intention of exemplifying his concept of fable, Aristotle transcribes two fables, including one from Aesop, a popular speaker to whom the paternity of the genre is attributed, and who, in his speeches, used the fable as a means of oratory demonstration: Aesop, in turn, when speaking publicly in Samos, at a time when the death penalty was being applied to a demagogue, told them how a fox, while crossing a river, was dragged into a precipice and, unable to get out, endured for a long time, in addition to being tormented by numerous ticks attached to its skin. A hedgehog that was wandering around, seeing her, approached sympathetically and asked if she wanted him to remove the ticks. But the fox did not allow it. And when the hedgehog asked her why, she replied: 'because these are already tired of me and suck very little blood; if you remove them, others will come hungry and suck the blood that I have left.' Also in your case, men of Samos, said Aesop, 'this man will not harm you anymore (because he is already rich), but if you kill him, others will come, poor, who will rob you and squander what you have left [21].'

Persuasion and conviction are two communication approaches that aim to influence and lead someone to adopt a certain idea, behavior, or point of view. Although these terms are often used interchangeably, they have some subtle differences in their application.

Persuasion involves the use of persuasive techniques and arguments to influence someone's opinion or action. It seeks to convince others through logical reasoning, evidence, relevant examples, and emotional appeal. Persuasion is a more comprehensive process and may involve building a strong case, anticipating objections, and presenting solutions to possible concerns. Successful persuasion requires an understanding of the needs, desires, and motivations of the target audience, as well as clear and effective communication.

On the other hand, conviction refers to the act of making someone believe or accept something without necessarily involving an argumentative or negotiating approach. Conviction can occur through different techniques, such as authority, reputation, emotional appeal, or trust. The goal is to create trust and credibility to influence someone's decision or behavior, often based on trust and a previously established relationship.

According to Silva and Santos (2021, p. 45):

Persuasion is a complex process that involves the use of communicative strategies to influence the attitudes, beliefs, and behaviors of other people. Conviction, on the other hand, refers to the ability to make someone believe or accept a certain idea or argument. Both are fundamental in the context of communication and can be explored in an ethical and effective way to achieve desired results [14].

Both approaches, persuasion, and conviction, have applications in various areas of life, such as sales, negotiation, leadership, politics, and marketing. However, it is important to remember that persuasion and conviction should be used ethically, transparently, and respectfully, respecting the opinions and autonomy of others.

It is important to emphasize that persuasion and conviction are skills that can be developed through practice and improvement of communication techniques. The competence to understand the target audience, adapt the message according to their needs and interests, present compelling arguments, and establish an emotional connection are key elements to achieve successful results in these areas.

4 Conclusion

The realization of training within organizations exists to increase their competitiveness in the market, enhance the growth and development of their employees. It is evident that well-trained employees make a significant difference,

consequently positively impacting the company's profits. However, the commercial sector is the biggest contributor to the company's profits, and what sets a salesperson apart is their power of communication.

The research fully met its objectives: to conceptualize organizational training and its practice in companies; to conceptualize communication and its development in individuals; to associate the practice of organizational training with the development of employees' communication skills; to analyze the main benefits of training for the development of communication skills in the commercial sector of organizations.

The study highlighted the need for companies to become increasingly aware of investing in training, especially in communication. It is essential to consider that for the commercial department, good public speaking and fluid, clear, objective, and, above all, emotional communication are indispensable since behind every customer is a human being driven by pure emotion.

Another significant point from the study worth emphasizing is that the approach to public speaking training should be focused on a commercial language, where sales professionals learn about persuasion and conviction techniques to generate sales and consequently increase competitiveness and organizational profits. In this way, as companies enhance their results, they also promote the development of their employees who participate in such training.

Finally, it is recommended that this practice be constant and implemented in organizations, providing continuous development to their employees. The alignment of training needs related to communication and sales should be a process that is part of the criteria and objectives adopted by the Commercial Management in collaboration with HR. It is worth noting that results achieved, commercial goals, attitudes, and behaviors will be transformed through business public speaking training, creating an environment of clarity, confidence, self-esteem, fluency, and creativity among employees and clients.

Compliance with ethical standards

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The authors assure that there is no conflict of interest with the publication of the manuscript or an institution or product mentioned in the manuscript and/or important for the result of the presented study.

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